

A systematic review on Internet Addiction and Mental Health of Adolescents

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Abstract: The internet has rapidly developed into one of the most critical components of our everyday lives. If we did not have access to the internet, it would be quite challenging for us to continue with our typical activities as they are now. Internet technology has seen widespread adoption, which has made it possible to bring together people from all over the world and paved the way for more productive ways to carry out ordinary chores in a variety of spheres of life. The internet is put to use for a number of functions that are essential; yet, it is also used for recreational activities such as navigating various social media platforms and playing games online. Maintaining a level of normalcy or mental composure in today's world, with all of its frenetic activity and cutthroat competition, is an extremely difficult task that requires a lot of effort. Even for people who are physically and psychologically strong, the modern world can make it challenging to maintain a healthy balance between one's mental and physical well-being. This research project aims to determine the elements that influence the mental health of adolescents as a result of their addiction to the internet, as well as the aspects that help promote the well-being of adolescents.

Keywords: Mental Health, adolescent, internet addiction, psychological well-being.

I. INTRODUCTION

The internet has quickly become one of the most important aspects of our life. It would be quite difficult for us to carry on with our regular activities if we did not have access to the internet. The widespread adoption of internet technology has made it possible to bring together individuals from all corners of the globe and paved the way for more productive ways to carry out routine tasks in a variety of sectors of life (Hawi, 2012).

However, despite its many benefits, the internet is not without its share of drawbacks. People have developed a dependence on it as a result, which makes it difficult for them to survive without it. The internet is put to use for a number of purposes that are vital, but it is also used recreational activities such as browsing social media platforms and playing games online (Dong et al., 2020; Jinet al., 2020). These routines eat up a significant amount of time for an individual, to the point that they are unable to simply relax without the presence of a device connected to the internet. It has been observed that there has been an increase in the level of internet addiction, which has a lot of adverse effects on their health and can even induce addiction.

Everyone is always in a rush and concerned about their daily routines because life has become so unpredictable. This way of living has clear repercussions, not just on mental health but also on physical health. The state of one's mental health is an essential component in the life of an individual (Cash et al., 2012). Due to the intense competition and hectic pace of modern life, it is a very challenging endeavour to maintain a level of normalcy or peace of mind. In today's environment, maintaining a healthy balance between one's mental and physical well-being can be difficult for even the most physically and mentally robust persons.

II. BACKGROUND

Nowadays, internet addiction has become a very popular term of westernisation, globalisation, and liberalisation. The Internet nowadays has become a fundamental aspect of one's life without which many people cannot envision their lives. It provides numerous amenities, becomes a source of enjoyment, searches for information, makes restaurants reservation searching maintains current concerning political and sociological concerns, etc. Nonetheless, it is an easily available source of information to the world and movable wireless technology (Van Rooji & Prause, 2014). Previously it is very tough to find any information regarding any use it takes lots of time and energy but owing to the internet, emails, and computer programming, such information is available at the tip of the figure. All these changes make people's life easier. It also provides the option of online shopping, online payment of bills, verifying some prior information, etc. yet the misuse of the internet usage produces addiction to it. Addiction to the internet is found in all ages all over the world (Griffiths et al., 2016).

People today would rather read articles on the internet than in newspapers or books because of its convenience. Recent years have seen a significant uptick in the rate at which adolescents engage in excessive internet use. In addition to this, it increased their reliance on the internet and mobile devices as they moved (Starcevic, 2013). Due to their addiction to the internet, some frequent users also struggle with psychological issues. When people are not online, they experience negative emotions such as depression, mood disorders, loneliness, and other similar feelings (Kurniasanti et al., 2019).

Websites are becoming an increasingly important topic of discussion among adolescents in today's society. They are devoting more of their time to using the internet and are devoting less of their time to engaging in activities that require physical movement. Unnecessarily, adolescents spend the majority of their time on their smartphones. It has an effect on a person's mental health as well as their ability to learn (Neverkovich et al., 2018; Cash et al., 2012). As a result of the proliferation of various technologies, there is a growing worry among adolescents over problems related to their mental health. Their addiction to the Internet interferes with their important life activities. The majority of adolescents use mobile phones, and downloading content might raise their stress levels. For starters, it may be difficult for them to do their daily homework at night, which can result in sleeping difficulties among adolescents (Mihajlov & Vejmelka, 2017). They much prefer conversing with their buddies online. This results in less time spent with the family. The internet is becoming increasingly relied upon as the primary source of information.

Adolescents who are dependent on the internet appear to have lower levels of functional connection when attaining distributed networks. Addiction to the internet in children and adolescents has been linked to a number of mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, and pressure on young people (Ryding & Kaye, 2018). In addition, studies have shown that strain can significantly predict internet dependency to a large extent. People who are addicted to alcohol, smoking, capsules, meals, or sexual activity have a higher risk of developing a net dependency because they need to once again deal with tension and difficulties through compulsive behaviour. This increases the likelihood that they will become addicted to something else (Noreen, 2013)

This research study focuses on identifying the influential dimensions that impacts the mental health of adolescents due to internet addiction and also the factors that helps in promoting the well-being of the adolescent.

III SOURCES

The research has made use of a systematic review, as was previously mentioned, and the databases Scopus and Web of Science are combed through in order to locate publications that may be incorporated into the review. These two databases contain a wide variety of scholarly works on a number of subjects, all of which were written by researchers from different parts of the world. As a consequence of this, these two databases are an ideal choice for compiling research publications. Keywords used in database searches include terms such as "Internet Addiction", "Online Addiction", "Mental Health", etc. The next section provides a full explanation of the process that was followed in order to complete the final articles. The search string involved in the process includes-

Search String Set 1 — ("Internet Addiction") AND ("Mental Health")

Search String Set 2 — ("Internet Addiction") AND ("Well-Being")

The next part will detail the method that was used to pick the search results that were generated using the aforementioned keywords once those results have been generated.

III.II DATA EXTRACTION AND SYNTHESIS

Use of a stringent technique to choose articles for final evaluation is one of the most critical criteria for successfully completing a systematic literature review. Other important criteria include: In the first step of the evaluation process, the articles are rated according to how relevant the titles are. After the connection between the title and the subject has been figured out, the abstract is given thorough consideration to see whether or not the overall work is up to par with the requirements. After doing an examination of the abstracts, the researchers chose the final publications to include in their study. After conducting extensive investigation, the most important topics that emerged from the final evaluation papers have been compiled into a list. The PRISMA that was built below features a flow chart that outlines the entire process.

Figure 1 – PRISMA

Source Author's own

II.III QUALITY PARAMETERS USED FOR SELECTION

In order to ensure that systematic review publications are of a high quality, Dyba & Dingsoyr (2008) devised a questionnaire checklist. The answers to these questions are graded based on how credible, rigorous, and relevant they are to the overall discussion. The items that were put forward for consideration are each given a score between one and zero based on how well they meet the aforementioned three quality standards. It's generally agreed that content with a score of four or higher is of a high enough standard to be considered for inclusion in the evaluation. You will find a table in the appendix with all of the different scores to help you better understand the method.

II.IV THREATS TO VALIDITY OF RESEARCH AND MITIGATIONS

Before carrying out a review, it is essential to perform an analysis of the construct as well as the external validity components. In order to address any injustices or dangers that may arise from validity concerns in the articles, Dyba & Dingsoyr, (2008) designed a quality assurance parameters checklist. This checklist is now being utilised. Second, the PRISMA method of gathering articles is the most effective tool for reducing the risks associated with the lack of authenticity.

III. RESULTS

The following is an account of the outcomes of the data extraction process that was carried out:

Sl. No.	Authors	Findings	Factors identified
1.	King et al., (2012)	It was observed that online interventions contribute to a decline in psychological health. Internet addiction creates melancholy and anxiety among the users.	Impulse control disorder
2.	Siomos et al., (2012)	According to the results of the study, an individual's approach to parenting may have an effect on whether or not they develop an addiction to the internet.	Parenting practices
3.	Xu et al., (2012)	The researchers investigated the impact that being addicted to the internet has on a student's ability to concentrate on their schoolwork. It was revealed that students' participation in online gaming was the most significant factor that influenced their academic achievement.	Internet addiction, academic achievement

4.	Bozkurt et al., (2013)	According to the findings, internet addiction is associated with harmful behaviour among adolescents.	Psychiatric disorder, internet addiction
5.	Goel et al., (2013)	According to the findings of the experts, adolescent users are more likely to develop an addiction to the internet. They made the observation that it generates a lot of issues pertaining to one's mental health.	Anxiety, depression
6.	Kuss et al., (2013)	The researchers indicated that the internet addiction is usually observed among adolescent. They observed that it creates a number of mental health concerns.	Internet addiction, depression, anxiety
7.	Wang et al., (2013)	The results of the study indicated that internet addiction influences the mental well-being of the youth negatively.	Predictor, well-being
8.	Adiele & Olatokun, (2014)	The researchers that conducted out this study got at the conclusion that addictive conduct is a key contributor to mental health disorders.	Internet addiction, "problematic internet use"
9.	Cunningham et al., (2014)	It was observed that internet interventions lead to deterioration of mental health. Internet addiction causes depression and anxiety among the users.	Depression, anxiety
10.	Ha & Hwang, (2014)	The researchers stated that the internet addiction is mostly observed among adolescent. They observed that it causes a number of mental health issues. Some of the most significant factors that were observed to be influenced by internet addiction are – depression, poor self health and subjective unhappiness.	depression, poor self health and subjective unhappiness
11.	Jiang, (2014)	The researchers analysed the influence of internet addiction on the academic performance of students. Online gaming was observed to be the most significant influencing factor that influenced the academic performance of the students.	Internet connectedness, academic performance
12.	Lam, (2014)	The researchers conducted a systematic review to analyse the risk factors of internet addiction. The researchers investigated the impact that being addicted to the internet has on a student's ability to concentrate on their schoolwork.	Academic performance, internet usage
13.	Lin et al., (2014)	The results of the study analysed the linkage between internet addiction and suicidal tendency among adolescents. A strong association was observed between the two variables.	Depression, lower self-esteem
14.	Tang et al., (2014)	The researchers that carried out this study arrived at the conclusion that addictive behaviour is a primary contributor to mental health conditions such as stress, anxiety, and depression.	Stress, psychological symptoms
15.	Singh & Barmola, (2015)	The findings of the study revealed that online interventions contribute to deterioration of mental health. Internet addiction creates melancholy and anxiety among the users.	Academic performance, internet addiction
16.	Kawabe et al., (2016)	The findings of the study suggested that internet addiction disrupts the life of an adolescent. The results suggested that internet addiction leads to problematic behaviour among the adolescents	"Problematic internet use"
17.	Ostovar et al., (2016)	Internet addiction is observed to be a leading factor in the development of procrastination patterns among young people. In addition to this, a number of psychological health disorders have emerged as a result. Addiction to the internet	Depression, anxiety, stress, loneliness

		contributes to a variety of maladaptive behaviours in young people.	
18.	Reinecke et al., (2016)	The researchers in this study observed that internet addiction has led to the cause of procrastination among the youth. This has also developed a number of psychological health disorders. Internet addiction causes a number of dysfunctional behaviours among youth.	Psychological health, stress, anxiety, depression
19.	Yayan et al., (2016)	The researchers stated that internet addiction causes social phobia as individuals are associating less with their social environment.	Social phobia, internet addicts
20.	Arslan, (2017)	According to the results of the study, being addicted to the internet can lead to a variety of psychological and social problems. The researchers endeavoured to find the characteristics that will aid folks in their fight against addiction and succeeding in this endeavour was their primary goal. It has been shown that the factors of mindfulness and self-forgiveness are the most beneficial factors in reducing the level of internet addiction among individuals. In addition, the researchers came to the conclusion that being isolated socially is one of the most significant factors contributing to internet addiction.	Mindfulness, forgiveness, psychological maltreatment
21.	Cerniglia et al., (2017)	It was observed that internet addiction leads to anxiety, social withdrawal, depression and family conflicts.	Social withdrawal, internet addiction
22.	Chou & Lee, (2017)	The findings of the study stated that internet addiction may be influenced by the parenting style adopted by the individual.	Internet parenting style, internet addiction tendency
23.	Johnson & Keane, (2017)	The researchers pointed out that the use of internet has changed the life of individuals. The excessive dependency on the internet however, leads to losing control over the time management among the individuals.	Time management, social use, digital pathologies
24.	Kurniasih, (2017)	The findings suggested the existence of a strong relationship between internet addiction and mental health disorders. The increased use of the internet causes the negative symptoms on the health of its users.	Mental disorder, disconnected, excessive use
25.	McNicol et al., (2017)	The researchers analysed the problems with identification and attachment that are caused by online addictions in this study. The problems were caused by people spending too much time online. Young adults with an addiction to the internet are likely to exhibit worried behaviour and become detached from their social context.	Distress, compulsive
26.	Monacis et al., (2017)	The researchers in this study analysed that issues related to identity and attachment that is arised due to online addictions. This might lead to anxious behaviour and detachment from the social environment among the young adults.	Anxious, avoidant
27.	Scott et al., (2017)	The researchers in this study raised concern on the excessive use of internet and the impact it has on the mental health. The increased use of internet has created a dependency on the social media and this has led to reduced social interactions among the individuals.	Depression, emotional intelligence, decreased self-motivation

28.	Sharma et al., (2017)	The researchers stated that addictions to technological devices are a cause of mental and physical health problems among its users.	Distress, psychosocial issues
29.	So et al., (2017)	Internet addiction has the tendency to cause hyperactivity disorder and behavioural addiction. The mental health of an individual degrades with the increase in the use of internet. The use of increased internet has led to causing ADHD among the individuals.	Hyperactivity disorder, internet addiction
30.	Tang et al., (2017)	The researchers analysed the impact that online gaming addition and other social media site addition has on the youth. The results indicated the existence of depressive symptoms and other psychological disorders.	Depressive symptoms, mood disturbances
31.	Tripathi, (2017)	The researcher evaluated the influence of internet addiction on mental health of the individuals. The researchers observed that internet gaming and internet addiction led to a number of health issues such as poor sleep quality, lower self-esteem and mood disorder.	Mindfulness, poor sleep quality, mood disorder, low self-esteem
32.	Yang et al., (2017)	It was observed that internet addiction has led to defining well being subjectively.	Subjective well-being, prosocial behaviour
33.	Anand et al., (2018)	The excessive use of internet causes distress and depression among the engineering students. The researchers observed that a number of socio demographic factors influence the cause of internet addiction among the engineering students.	Depression, psychological distress, internet addiction
34.	Arpaci et al., (2017)	It was observed that a psychological need of an individual leads to internet addiction in an individual.	Affiliation, dominance, achievement, autonomy
35.	Bisen & Deshpande, (2018)	The researchers here have addressed internet addiction as a disorder and have stated that internet addiction is a cause of problems in every sphere of their life. These problems extend to the family, academia and occupation.	Family problems, academic problems, occupational problems
36.	Griffiths, (2018)	Internet addiction and online gaming addiction is a disorder that is observed among the young adults. These are a root of a number of health related issues among them.	Time spent online
37.	Gupta et al., (2018)	The researchers in this study identified that addictive behaviour leads to depression, anxiety and stress.	Depression, stress, anxiety
38.	Lee et al., (2018)	The researchers determined the psychosocial factors that are linked with the excessive usage of the smartphone. The results indicated that the users tend to develop poor communication skills, high level of emotional problems and also they tend to have a lower self-esteem.	Poor communication quality, emotional problems, lower self esteem
39.	Milani et al., (2018)	Internet addiction causes a number of dysfunctional behaviour among the individuals. These leads to a social and psychological problems that is faced by the individuals.	Psychological adjustment
40.	O'Reilly et al., (2018)	Social media has the potential to create addiction among its users. The excessive use of social media promotes negative influence the health of the adolescents.	Anxiety, cyberbullyig, mental wellbeing
41.	Baturay & Toker, (2019)	Internet addiction and online gaming addiction hinders the psychological health of an individual.	Decreased self-confidence , decreased social self-efficacy, loneliness, poor sleep pattern

42.	Grau et al., (2019)	The researchers in this study evaluated the social media addiction among the millennial. The results indicated that marketing plays a very significant role on social media addiction.	Social media addiction, near addiction
43.	Hsieh et al., (2019)	The results in this study observed that the young adults feel pressurised by their peers to use internet. The social pressure to use internet and social media platforms has led to the anxiety and stress among the young population.	Psychological distress, emotional intelligence, social intelligence
44.	Jahan et al., (2019)	The findings of the study suggested that with the increase in the level of internet addiction in an individual causes a deterioration in the sleep quality.	Sleep quality, internet addiction
45.	Jeri-Yabar et al., (2019)	The researchers in this study stated that the increased use of internet has led to developing a dependence on the social network websites and has led to causing depression among the users of internet.	Depression, social network dependence
46.	Song & Park, (2019)	It was observed that the self-control and mindfulness negatively impact the mindfulness and self-control of the individuals. The researchers stated that the internet addiction has a number of negative impacts on an individual and requires to be controlled to mitigate the health issues.	Mindfulness, self-control
47.	Vadher et al., (2019)	The researcher in this study observed that the use of internet has led to problematic behaviour among the adolescents. The quality of sleep and quality of life was observed to deteriorate with the excessive use of internet.	Poor sleep quality, poor quality of life
48.	Wang, (2019)	The findings of the study stated that the boredom and leisure time has increased the usage of internet among the adolescents. The increased leisure time and cause of boredom increased the inclination of the individuals to use the internet.	Leisure time, boredom, internet addiction
49.	Hassan et al., (2020)	The researchers focused on identifying the associated variables that causes internet addiction among the young adults. It was observed that certain factors such as the living set-up of the individual, the relationship shared with the family and the physical activity indulged in has a potential to influence the level of internet addiction among the young adults.	living set-up, detached family relationship, and physical activity
50.	Karaca et al., (2020)	The results of the study indicated that online gaming addiction causes social P among the adolescents and this can be observed across the various socio-demographic variables of a population.	Social anxiety
51.	Lin et al., (2020)	The findings were conclusive of the fact that internet addiction acts as a link between cyber victimisation and negative psychological and physical symptoms on its users. The researchers also stated that by indulging in physical and mental exercises the users can minimise the negative impact of internet addiction.	Exercise, physical activity
52.	Prochnow et al., (2020)	It was observed that online gaming addiction has led to depressive symptoms among the users and lack of social skills.	Depressive symptoms, social support
53.	Berte et al., (2021)	The association between the two factors i.e. internet addiction and self-efficacy was analysed in this study. The	Internet addiction, depression, suicidal ideation

		results obtained demonstrated that internet addiction has the tendency to adversely impact the level of self-efficacy among university students. This was irrespective the age, gender and academic level of the students.	
54.	Hu et al.,(2021)	The researchers stated that psychological sushi can help youth to modify their internet addiction behaviour.	Psychological sushi internet addiction
55.	Mamun et al., (2021)	It was observed that the excessive use of internet among the students who are seeking jobs tends to cause a number of psychological issues. These issues were caused due to excessive use of the internet.	Depression, stress, anxiety
56.	Thompson et al., (2021)	It was identified that the internet addiction has led to creating privacy concerns.	Privacy, self-disclosure, information security
57.	Arslan & Coskun, (2022)	Internet addiction was observed to cause a number of psychosocial issues. The researchers attempted to identify the factors that will help in overcome the addiction among individuals. The factors mindfulness and self-forgiveness were observed to be the most effective factors in reducing the level of internet addiction among the individuals. The researchers further, observed that social exclusion is a major influencing factor of internet addiction	Self- forgiveness and mindfulness
58.	Ozaslan et al., (2022)	The excessive use of internet has led to the degrading relationship between the parents and the young adults. It also leads to a number of mental health issues among them.	Problematic internet usage, peer problems, emotional symptoms, hyperactivity
59.	Romero-Rodriguez et al., (2022)	The researchers stated that the internet use causes problematic behaviour on the users. This was mostly observed among the students. The researchers stated that there is a need to mitigate the negative impact of internet addiction in order to promote healthy lifestyle among the youth.	Problematic internet use, internet addiction

IV. DISCUSSION

A recent study came to the conclusion that adolescent internet users have a greater risk of developing an addiction to the internet. They came to the conclusion that it causes a great deal of problems that are associated with a person's mental health (Goel et al., 2013). According to the findings of Kuss et al. (2013), addiction to the internet is most commonly seen in adolescents. They made the observation that it generates a lot of issues pertaining to one's mental health. Addiction-like behaviour on the internet is a significant factor in the development of mental illnesses such as stress, anxiety, and depression (Adiele & Olatokun, 2014). Researchers Jer-Yabar et al. (2019) claimed that rising usage of the internet has led to the development of a dependence on the social network websites, which in turn has led to the causing of depression among users of the internet.

According to research conducted by Cunningham et al., (2014), participation in online interventions is associated with a decline in mental health. Addiction to the internet can lead to feelings of despair and anxiety among users. Addiction to the internet can lead to a variety of mental health problems. Depression, poor self-health, and subjective unhappiness are some of the most significant characteristics that have been identified to be altered by internet addiction (Ha & Hwang, 2014). In addition, Tang et al. (2014) came to the conclusion that addictive behaviour is a main factor in the development of health issues. In addition to this, a number of psychological health disorders have emerged as a result. Addiction to the internet contributes to a variety of maladaptive behaviours in young people (Reinecke, et al., 2016). Addiction to the internet has also been linked to feelings of worry and social isolation, as well as depression and conflict within families (Cerniglia et al., 2017; Gupta et al., 2018). Researchers Anand et al., 2017 reported that the cause of internet addiction among engineering students is influenced by a number of socio demographic parameters.

According to the findings of a recent study, participation in online treatments is associated with a decline in one's mental health. Addiction to the internet can lead to feelings of depression and anxiety in its users (Singh & Barmola, 2015). Young adults are

made to feel as though they are under pressure from their peers to use the internet. The young generation is experiencing increased levels of worry and stress as a result of the societal pressure to use internet platforms (Hsieh et al., 2019).

According to the findings of a study, the manner in which a parent raises their children may have some bearing on whether or not their child eventually develops an addiction to the internet (Siomos et al., 2012). An individual's parenting approach might have an effect on whether or not they develop an addiction to the internet (Chou & Lee, 2017). The unhealthy amount of time spent on the internet has contributed to a deterioration in the relationship between parents and young adults. In addition to this, it causes a variety of mental health problems. (Ozaslan et al., 2022).

It has been found that students' addiction to the Internet has a negative impact on their academic performance. Being addicted to the internet influences a student's ability to concentrate on their studies. It was discovered that the students' engagement in online gaming was the single most important factor that influenced their academic progress (Xu et al., 2012; Jian, 2014). Researchers Bisen & Deshpande, (2018) have discussed internet addiction as an illness in this article, and they have said that internet addiction is a cause of issues in every aspect of a person's life. They stated that these challenges extend to the family, academia and occupation. Berte et al. (2021) examined the relationship between the two factors, namely internet addiction and self-efficacy, and came to the conclusion that there is a correlation between the two. The findings that were obtained showed that an addiction to the internet has a propensity to have a negative impact on the level of self-efficacy that is present among university students. This was the case regardless of the students' ages, genders, or levels of academic achievement.

Summarising the literature study conducted the following conceptual framework is conceived:

The conceptual model signifies the influence internet addiction has on mental health issues. It also portrays the psychological well-being factors that help in mitigating the influence of internet addiction.

V. CONCLUSION

A person who has good mental health is able to adapt readily to both environmental conditions and interpersonal relationships. Mental health is defined as both the development and the functioning of wholesome and balanced mental functioning. Mental health is defined as "the skill in which others support an individual to seek an adjustment in the challenging events of their life". The mental health of an individual is observed to be impacted by a number of factors. Internet addiction is one such factor that influences mental health of an individual.

Internet addiction affects the mental fitness of those who replace genuine, loving relationships with virtual ones. People who are addicted to the mainstream version of the internet have a history of depression, tension, and pressure. A lack of self-esteem has also been observed with the assistance of various researchers; the amount of time these individuals spend using the internet isolates them from others at the same time as it contributes to an increase in their feelings of depression. The youngsters in the give-up are the ones who are primarily affected by the never-ending cycle of depression.

People who are addicted to the internet exhibit their worry in a variety of ways, like checking their texts and emails in the middle of the night after immediately waking up from sleep or connecting to the internet as the first thing they do when they wake up in the morning. Detachment from the truth, dozing problems, persistent stress if now not being online for hours, social isolation, and occupational malfunctioning circumstance are all factors that lead to the character experiencing a serious case of melancholy

and tension. According to the findings of several studies, engagement in online treatments is related with a deterioration in one's mental health. Users who are addicted to the internet may experience feelings of hopelessness and anxiety as a result of their behaviour. An addiction to the internet can result in a range of issues related to one's mental health. Depression, poor self-health, and subjective unhappiness are some of the most prominent traits that have been discovered as being impacted by internet addiction. Other qualities that have been found to be affected include anxiety and irritability. In addition, addictive behaviours are a primary contributor to the growth of mental health conditions like stress, anxiety, and depression.

The research study here developed a theoretical framework that connects the association between mental health issues, internet addiction, and psychological well-being. The conceptual model framed here is based on literature study conducted. There is however, a need to conduct an empirical research to analyse the association of these factors.

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